

Text to Speech

Using text-to-speech software with a variety of texts.

Texts

Using these tools in this scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

More free features?

Help?

Simpler processes?

Text to Speech

Using text-to-
speech
software to fill
in forms online

Existing tools

Using these tools in this
scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

Integrated
microphone?

Help?

Simpler
processes?

Text to Speech

Using text-
to-speech to
send
messages

Existing tools

Using these tools in this
scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

Integrated
microphone?

Help?

Simpler
processes?

